

Madeira's Entrepreneurship and the Shift in Incentive Strategies

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to evaluate the evolution of the incentive strategies of the *Instituto de Emprego da Madeira, IP-RAM* (IEM), which translated means Madeira Employment Institute, and their impact on the number of approved projects, jobs created and promoters/entrepreneurs that emerged. It also aims to evaluate the characteristics of the jobs created, promoters or non-promoters, their evolution, and interconnection with the literature review. In order to analyze the evolution of the entrepreneurship programs of the Madeira Employment Institute, and the characteristics of the jobs and promoters (unemployed entrepreneurs who apply for an entrepreneurship program), secondary data obtained from its annual balance reports (*Emprego e Coesão Social - Breve Balanço* reports), from 2011 to 2022, available on the institution's website, at <https://www.iem.madeira.gov.pt/estatisticas-anuais/>, where data were obtained for the period between 2009 and 2022, using a quantitative methodology and where they demonstrate the different types of programs that the Madeira Employment Institute had or has throughout the period under analysis. Global analysis of entrepreneurship programs for the unemployed in recent years, their evolution over time, and the perception of whether the objectives of government institutions are being met, as well as the analysis of the jobs created, entrepreneurs or non-entrepreneurs, depending on their characteristics. One of the main objectives of the Madeira Employment Institute is being fulfilled, which is to rationalize resources in a better way, giving greater focus to the creation of jobs globally, as well as confirming some propositions of the revision of literature, among the articles analyzed, namely in terms of the characteristics of the jobs created, promoters or non-promoters, verifying a greater propensity for entrepreneurship among male individuals who were young adults, as well as the evolution of the jobs created in terms of level of education, which has been increasingly high. This study contributes to a possible basis for a comparative analysis between regions and institutions that work to encourage entrepreneurship, as well as to understand which aspects government entities should still work on, in order to improve their results.

KEYWORDS: Unemployed, Entrepreneurship, Employment, Evolution, IEM, Programs

INTRODUCTION

Government policies play a key role in propensity for entrepreneurship, both nationally and internationally, as well as regionally. A region that does not promote measures to support entrepreneurship, or that hinders, through its laws, policies and culture, the entrepreneurial intention, tends not to be as competitive as those that facilitate its existence, which may lead to that in economic terms it becomes distance more and more. In economic aspects, the problems of unemployment also stand out, which not only concerns a social problem, but also the regional competitiveness previously mentioned.

In this context, it is intended to study the evolution of government policies implemented in the Autonomous Region of Madeira, through the regional Employment Institute, namely the programs created themselves, to encourage the entrepreneurship of the unemployed, as well as to study the evolution over time of the jobs created, promoters or non-promoters, and the propensity for entrepreneurship, or for entering the labor market according to its characteristics (gender, educational qualifications, age and previous professional experiences), interconnecting it with the literature review. The present study will have as analysis timeline the period between 2009 and 2022.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

ENTREPRENEURSHIP

Based on the works of Joseph A. Schumpeter, Howard H. Stevenson, Peter F. Drucker, William B. Gartner, Saras D. Sarasvathy, Scott A. Shane, Eric Ries, Julian Birkinshaw and Shaker A. Z. S. A. Mega, we can see that entrepreneurship it is widely recognized as an important driver of economic growth, job creation and innovation (Table I).

Schumpeter, one of the most influential economists of the 20th century, emphasized the role of the entrepreneur in driving economic growth through innovation. Stevenson, in turn, considered entrepreneurship as a search for opportunities beyond

controlled resources. Drucker argued that entrepreneurship involves creating something new and distinctive, while Gartner explored the distinction between entrepreneurship and small business ownership.

More recent authors, such as Sarasvathy, introduced concepts such as the effect and use of resources and partnerships to create enterprises. Shane emphasized the importance of access to capital and other resources for entrepreneurs, while Ries advocated using what-if methodologies to reduce risk and increase the success rate. Birkinshaw explored the challenges of entrepreneurship in large organizations, while mega investigated the role of social entrepreneurship in addressing global challenges.

Understanding these authors' ideas and perspectives contributes to a better understanding of the challenges and opportunities faced by entrepreneurs, highlighting their contribution to economic and social progress.

Table I. Definitions of Entrepreneurship by different authors

Author	Definition of Entrepreneurship	Year
Joseph A. Schumpeter	It is a process of creative destruction, in which entrepreneurs introduce disruptive innovations, move away from old production methods and create new products, processes and markets, causing economic and social changes.	1942
Howard H. Stevenson	It is the process of creating, launching and growing new projects, which involves identifying and exploiting opportunities, acquiring and allocating resources, innovation, leadership and management, with the aim of creating value and generating economic and social impact .	1985
Peter F. Drucker	It is the search for opportunities, based on existing and/or new resources, with the aim of creating economic and social value, involving the identification, evaluation and exploitation of opportunities, resource allocation, risk taking and decision making. in uncertain environments.	1986
William B. Gartner	It is a social and economic process, which involves identifying and exploiting opportunities, creating and growing new ventures, and generating economic and social value.	1988
Scott A. Shane	It is the process of identifying and exploiting opportunities, based on the resources, skills and experiences of entrepreneurs, with a view to creating and growing new ventures, innovation and generating economic and social value.	2003
Saras D. Sarasvathy	It is a decision-making process, based on an approach that involves identifying and exploiting opportunities, taking risks, learning from action, and adapting to environmental conditions and contingencies.	2008
Eric Ries	It is a mutual process of experimentation, learning and adaptation, which involves the continuous creation and validation of hypotheses, the development of innovative products and services, and the search for value creation, based on constant feedback from the market and users.	2011
Julian Birkinshaw	It is a process of creating, developing and implementing new ideas and opportunities, within or outside existing organizations, with the aim of improving performance and competitiveness.	2012
Van Gelderen et al.,	It is a dynamic process that involves identifying and taking advantage of business opportunities, resource allocation and value creation.	2015
Tavassoli et al.,	Entrepreneurship can be defined as the identification, evaluation and exploitation of opportunities for the creation of economic, social or cultural value through the creation of new companies or through innovation in existing companies.	2021

PROPENSITY FOR ENTREPRENEURSHIP ACCORDING TO CHARACTERISTICS

Entrepreneurship propensity refers to an individual's inclination or predisposition to initiate and manage an entrepreneurial project. It is a multidimensional construction that encompasses several cognitive, affective and behavioral characteristics that differentiate entrepreneurs from non-entrepreneurs.

Scholars have extensively investigated the factors that shape the propensity for entrepreneurship, including demographic variables, personal factors, environmental factors, and cultural values. For example, several studies have shown that individuals with a higher level of education, professional experience and financial resources are more likely to become entrepreneurs (Shane, 2003; van Praag and Versloot, 2007). Likewise, personality traits such as self-efficacy, locus of control and risk-taking have been shown to be positively correlated with entrepreneurial intentions (Zhao et al., 2005; Rauch and Frese, 2007).

In terms of personal factors, gender and age are particularly relevant. Verheul et al. (2005) and Marlow, S., & McAdam, M. (2013) suggest that women are less likely to be involved in entrepreneurial activities than men. Several factors have been pointed out to explain this gender disparity, including the presence of gender stereotypes, which can limit women's opportunities in areas such as funding, access to networks and public recognition. In addition, they point out that women also face challenges related to the balance between work and personal life, which can make it difficult to reconcile their entrepreneurial activities with other responsibilities.

Regarding age, Reynolds et al. (2005) suggest that the propensity for entrepreneurship is higher among young adults and decreases with age. This pattern can be explained by a greater willingness of young adults to take risks and explore new business opportunities. In addition, Shane (2009) points out that age can affect individuals' willingness to take financial and personal risks, as well as their ability to acquire resources and skills necessary for entrepreneurship.

However, Bosma et al. (2012) state that it is important to note that these trends may vary according to the cultural and socioeconomic context. For example, in countries where employment opportunities are limited, the propensity for entrepreneurship may be higher across all age groups and genders.

Additionally, environmental factors such as access to entrepreneurial networks, availability of finance and regulatory frameworks have also been shown to influence the propensity for entrepreneurship (Gnyawali and Fogel, 1994; Reynolds et al., 2005). Finally, cultural values such as individualism, innovation and propensity for risk are also preponderant for the progress of entrepreneurship, with studies indicating that individuals from countries with higher levels of these values are more likely to become entrepreneurs (Hofstede, 2001; Estrin et al., 2013).

Despite extensive research on the subject, there is still an ongoing debate among scholars about the exact nature of the relationship between these factors and the propensity for entrepreneurship. Some argue that there are significant individual differences in entrepreneurial propensity that cannot be fully explained by demographic or psychological factors (Gartner, 1988). Others suggest that the role of culture and environment should be further considered in understanding entrepreneurship propensity (Shane and Venkataraman, 2000).

Briefly, the propensity for entrepreneurship is a complex and multidimensional construction that encompasses several individual, environmental and cultural factors. While much remains to be learned about the nature and determinants of entrepreneurial propensity, existing research highlights the importance of individual traits, environmental factors, and cultural values in shaping entrepreneurial intentions and behaviors.

FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE ENTREPRENEURSHIP

Entrepreneurship is a complex activity that involves the creation and development of new businesses, products or services. The scientific literature has pointed out several factors that influence both the decision to become an entrepreneur and the success of the enterprise.

According to Shane and Venkataraman (2000), the business environment is one of the most significant factors that influence entrepreneurship. Well-established companies in a given area can inhibit the emergence of new ventures, while areas with less business development can stimulate it. In addition, government policies such as tax incentives and training programs for entrepreneurs can also affect entrepreneurship (Audretsch et al., 2015).

Social capital is another relevant factor for entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurs with a solid, quality network of contacts tend to be more successful than those who don't. The collaboration and support of other entrepreneurs, investors and mentors can help to overcome the initial challenges and increase the chances of success, being corroborated by authors such as Adler and Kwon (2002) and Burt (1997).

The authors Audretsch et al. (2015) also point out that the level of education also influences entrepreneurship. The higher the educational level of the entrepreneur, the more likely he is to succeed in relation to the others. In this way, education can help in the development of skills necessary for entrepreneurship, such as planning, financial management and leadership.

The intrinsic characteristics of the entrepreneur are also important factors. Self-efficacy, that is, the belief that one can perform difficult tasks, is a relevant trait for successful entrepreneurs. Other equally important traits include motivation, perseverance and the ability to take risks. Studies by authors such as Bandura et al., (1999) and McClelland (1961) support the importance of these characteristics.

It is also relevant to mention the cultural environment, as cultures that value innovation and risk are more likely to have a greater number of entrepreneurs, in contrast to cultures that discourage it, risking compromising the creation of new ventures, as corroborated by Hofstede (2001) and Gundry et al. (2014).

Thus, it is essential to understand and identify these factors that prove to be useful for the creation of government policies and practical initiatives, boosting the development of new entrepreneurs.

With the aim of corroborating the aforementioned factors, the study by Teixeira et al. (2018) complements this knowledge, analyzing the European panorama and providing understanding of how entrepreneurship factors can vary according to different contexts. The article by Teixeira et al. (2018) reveals that education represents a preponderant factor for entrepreneurial intention in countries like Portugal and Spain, but not in countries like Switzerland and Norway. This indicates that the influence of education may vary according to the cultural and economic context of each country.

Furthermore, the article by Teixeira et al. (2018) also suggests that factors such as age, gender, previous entrepreneurial experience and access to finance can influence entrepreneurial intentions, emphasizing the importance of considering them in the analysis of entrepreneurship.

GOVERNMENT POLICIES TO SUPPORT ENTREPRENEURSHIP

Entrepreneurship has been increasingly recognized as an important force for the global economy. In this context, government policies to support entrepreneurship are essential for the development of new ventures and job creation.

One of the most effective policies to support entrepreneurship is the provision of tax incentives. These incentives can include tax breaks for new ventures or tax breaks for companies that create jobs. According to several authors, including Audretsch et al. (2015), these incentives can be fundamental to stimulate the creation of new companies and encourage economic growth.

Another important government policy is the availability of financing for new ventures. This could include low-interest loans or grants for new ventures. Some authors, such as Shane and Cable (2002), argue that lack of funding is one of the main barriers to entrepreneurship. Therefore, the availability of affordable finance is critical to supporting new ventures.

The creation of education and training programs for entrepreneurs is also an important government policy. These programs may include training courses in business management, marketing, finance and other skills essential to the success of a new venture. Authors such as Brush et al. (2003) and Katz and Green (2009) argue that education and training are key to successful entrepreneurship.

The creation of business incubators and accelerators is another important government policy to support entrepreneurship. These institutions provide workspace, business support and access to finance for new ventures. Authors such as Hackett and Dilts (2004) claim that business incubators and accelerators are essential to support the development of new ventures.

Finally, creating networks of entrepreneurs and mentors is also an important government policy. These networks offer support and guidance to new entrepreneurs, helping them overcome challenges and develop their entrepreneurial skills. Authors such as Adler and Kwon (2002) and Chesbrough (2010) defend the importance of these networks to support entrepreneurship.

In short, government policies to support entrepreneurship can include tax incentives, affordable funding, training and capacity building programs, business incubators and accelerators, and networks of entrepreneurs and mentors. Implementing these policies can be instrumental in supporting new venture creation and economic growth.

BACKGROUND IN PORTUGAL AND THE AUTONOMOUS REGION OF MADEIRA

Entrepreneurship has been recognized as an important driver of economic growth and job creation, and Portugal and the Autonomous Region of Madeira are no exception. In Portugal, there are several public policies and programs to encourage entrepreneurship that aim to encourage the development of startups and innovative businesses (IAPMEI - *Agência para a Competitividade e Inovação*, I.P., 2023). Among the most important government initiatives are Startup Portugal (Startup Portugal, 2023), which aims to create a stronger and more dynamic entrepreneurial ecosystem across the country, and Portugal Ventures (*História, Visão e Valores* - Portugal Ventures, 2023), which is a venture capital fund that invests in innovative startups and small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) with high growth potential.

In the Autonomous Region of Madeira, entrepreneurship has also been an important vector of economic development. AJEM (*Associação de Jovens Empresários Madeirenses*, 2023), which is the Association of Young Madeiran Entrepreneurs, has

played a key role in supporting and promoting new companies and startups. AJEM has developed training, mentoring and incubation projects, in addition to establishing partnerships with public and private entities in order to encourage entrepreneurship in the region.

Nevertheless, Startup Madeira (Startup Madeira, 2023) is another important initiative in the region, which offers support to entrepreneurs in the form of incubation, acceleration and financing. The business incubator has been central to supporting the creation of new companies in the Autonomous Region of Madeira, as well as helping entrepreneurs to develop their projects and business ideas.

It is also relevant to address the various initiatives implemented by the Regional Government of Madeira, in order to stimulate entrepreneurship and improve the business environment. These initiatives include establishing business incubators, financially supporting startups, creating a mentor network and promoting networking events. However, there is still room for improvement in the region's entrepreneurship ecosystem, including developing infrastructure and promoting a stronger entrepreneurial culture. An example of a public institution that adopts measures to encourage entrepreneurship is the *Instituto de Emprego da Madeira, IP-RAM* (IEM), which translated means Madeira Employment Institute.

THE MADEIRA EMPLOYMENT INSTITUTE (IEM) AND ITS PROGRAMS

The mission of this public body is “the coordination and implementation of the employment policy in the Autonomous Region of Madeira, promoting the creation and quality of employment and combating unemployment, through the implementation of active measures and actions to promote employment”, and its vision is “to find, at all times, the best answers for those who need support in the area of employment” (*Missão, Visão e Valores - IEM, 2023*).

Unlike the IEFPP, that is, the Institute of Employment and Professional Training on the Portugal mainland, IEM focuses mainly on the area of employment, with the part of professional training managed under the supervision of the Regional Secretariat for Education, Science and Technology, through the *Instituto para a Qualificação, IP-RAM* (IQ, IP-RAM, 2023), which translated means Institute for Qualification, while the Employment Institute, is under the supervision of the Regional Secretariat for Social Inclusion and Citizenship (*Instituto de Emprego da Madeira, IP-RAM, 2023*).

In this sense, the Madeira Employment Institute seeks to combat unemployment in the region, through measures in favor of the population, namely acting as an intermediary institution between companies/entities and workers looking for a job. In addition to the Job Center, the Employment Institute also has an Employment Programs Department, which seeks, through financial incentives granted to companies and/or other entities (directly or indirectly), to provide an opportunity for an internship, occupational program or employment contract, to the unemployed registered in the institution (*Instituto de Emprego da Madeira, IP-RAM, 2023*).

In this way, and in addition to benefiting the registered unemployed, through the offer of a placement, the Employment Institute also emerges as an institution that widely assists companies, since, in addition to being an intermediary in the recruitment of potential workers (by improving the efficiency in the search for human resources), it also provides financial benefits (whether through reimbursements or through bonuses), through existing programs (*Instituto de Emprego da Madeira, IP-RAM, 2023*).

In addition to the connection between entities and users, the Employment Institute also gives the unemployed the opportunity to create their own business, that is, to create their own job. In this way, not only are opportunities at the level of employment for third parties given, but this institution also offers opportunities at the level of entrepreneurship, with financial and management support being granted to new companies created, within the scope of these programs (*Instituto de Emprego da Madeira, IP-RAM, 2023*).

During the period under review, from 2009 to 2022, have taken place or are in progress the programs CPE – Creation of Own Employment, PADE – Support Program for Unemployed Entrepreneurs, PEED – Program to Stimulate Entrepreneurship for Unemployed People, CRIEE – Program for the Creation of Companies and Employment and eJovem – Young Entrepreneur Program.

Let us now proceed to the explanation of each of the programs in question.

CPE - CREATION OF OWN EMPLOYMENT (2001 - CURRENTLY)

Governed by Ordinance number 101/2001 of September 6th, published in the Official Journal of the Autonomous Region of Madeira, Series I, number 88, this program to combat unemployment aims at creating one's own employment, upon payment of a

of the total amount of unemployment benefits, provided that the unemployed person presents a business idea/project that ensures full-time employment, and that demonstrates economic and financial viability, and may even benefit from an extra subsidy called in English “Special Subsidy”, when the overall amount of unemployment benefits proves to be insufficient to carry out the project (IEM, *Relatório Emprego e Coesão Social: Breve Balanço* 2011, 2012). In this way, this program is very important in combating, not only the unemployment of users who, through articulation between Social Security and the Madeira Employment Institute, can benefit from an entrepreneurship program for the creation of their own job, but also very relevant to increase the levels of entrepreneurship in the Autonomous Region of Madeira, through the creation of new businesses and companies.

PADE – SUPPORT PROGRAM FOR UNEMPLOYED ENTREPRENEURS (2009 - 2013)

The PADE program was created through Ordinance number 74/2009 of July 10, and aimed to “encourage and support the creation of their own jobs by unemployed people with an entrepreneurial spirit, as well as contributing to the eventual creation of other jobs necessary for the development of the said project”, provided that it was economically, financially and technically viable. Candidates for this program could be unemployed people who found themselves in that situation involuntarily, who had been registered for more than 12 months, or young people aged up to 24 who had not had more than 6 months of professional experience as an employed person. This program, included financial support in the form of non-refundable subsidies, in terms of investment, up to 60% of the eligible investment, and which could be added a reimbursable subsidy, in eligible cases, and in terms of job creation, corresponding to 18 times the minimum monthly wage for each job created. The latter could be increased with bonuses and premiums depending on the characteristics of the workers hired. Unemployed people who were recipients of unemployment benefits should apply for the attribution of the payment of unpaid benefits in a single payment, an amount that enters into the calculation of the investment support granted, in the non-refundable subsidy component (IEM, *Relatório Emprego e Coesão Social: Breve Balanço* 2011, 2012).

PEED – PROGRAM TO STIMULATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP FOR UNEMPLOYED PEOPLE (2013 - 2020)

Created through Ordinance number 32/2013, of May 13, PEED maintained the same objective as PADE, the program that replaced it, and included financial support for job creation and investment. This was a very important instrument in view of the increased demand for solutions for entrepreneurship and for creating their own jobs, reflecting “the risk and challenge that unemployed people decided to assume and face”, constituting itself as a response, not only to the problem of unemployment, but also to encourage entrepreneurship. This program allowed access to amounts higher than the CPE, and its creation was carried out with the aim of better rationalizing resources, with greater focus on job creation (IEM, *Relatório Emprego e Coesão Social: Breve Balanço* 2013, 2014).

CRIEE – PROGRAM FOR THE CREATION OF COMPANIES AND EMPLOYMENT (2020 - CURRENTLY)

The CRIEE program is governed by Ordinance number 16/2020, of February 6, maintaining the same objective of the PADE and PEED programs, a program that replaced the latter, and also includes financial support for the creation of jobs and investment. Compared to the PEED, the CRIEE program now provides for the possibility for promoters (unemployed entrepreneurs who apply for the program) to attend a training course in the area of management (both in the project analysis phase and in the follow-up phase), when necessary, this expense being eligible. Increases are foreseen in terms of hiring the very long-term unemployed (registered at the employment center for at least 24 months), as well as in terms of job creation in the areas of the blue, green and/or circular economy, and for projects based in rural councils with a resident population of less than 15,000 inhabitants. At the moment, within the scope of this program, the processes of payment to promoters are simplified in just two moments, with the first appearing after the signature of the contract, and the second after the creation of all the proposed jobs and proof of application of allocated amounts (IEM, *Relatório 2020: Emprego e Coesão Social - Breve Balanço*, 2020).

EJOVEM – YOUNG ENTREPRENEUR PROGRAM (2022 - CURRENTLY)

eJovem, created by Ordinance number 106/2022 of March 2nd, comes with a special focus on unemployed young people aged between 18 and 29 years old, aiming to stimulate their entrepreneurial spirit and the creation of their own job, integrating prior theoretical training in the area of management (180 hours over 2 months, with the right to subsidize food and transport), financial support for the project to create jobs and companies, and support at the level of consultancy in its implementation where necessary.

In this way, conditions are provided for young people to acquire the knowledge, skills and abilities necessary to create a project based on a business idea, aiming at its successful implementation and economic growth. Candidates who present a viable investment project, which leads to job creation, are awarded financial support per job created (maximum 4), in the amount equivalent to 10 times the IAS (Social Support Index), with an increase of up to 30% depending on the characteristics of the placement, and financial investment support of up to 15 times the IAS for each job created and up to a limit of four, also being increased in cases where the project falls within the scope of the economy blue, green and/or circular, in the technological area, or if it is located in a municipality with less than 15 thousand residents (IEM, *Relatório 2022: Emprego e Coesão Social - Breve Balanço*, 2022).

METHODOLOGY

In order to give color to the analysis of the subject in question, secondary data obtained from the annual balance reports of the *Instituto de Emprego da Madeira, IP-RAM (relatórios Emprego e Coesão Social - Breve Balanço)*, from 2011 to 2022, published on the institution's website, at <https://www.iem.madeira.gov.pt/estatisticas-anuais/>, where data were obtained for the period between 2009 and 2022, using a quantitative methodology.

Data referring to the programs CPE – Creation of Own Employment, PADE – Support Program for Unemployed Entrepreneurs, PEED – Program to Stimulate Entrepreneurship for Unemployed People, CRIEE – Program for Creation of Companies and Employment and eJovem – Young Entrepreneur Program were withdrawn.

Table II distinguishes the different programs by their nature and permanence over time, in the period under review from 2009 to 2022.

Table II. Distinction of the different IEM programs by their nature, between 2009 and 2022, prepared by the authors, based on the IEM annual balance reports

	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Specific program for beneficiaries of unemployment benefits	CPE													
More generic program	PADE				PEED						CRIEE			
Specific program for young people	(did not exist)													eJovem

Table III shows the evolution of the CPE, PADE, PEED and CRIEE programs between 2009 and 2022, based on the annual balance reports of the IEM (*relatórios Emprego e Coesão Social - Breve Balanço*), between 2011 to 2022. Although the eJovem program is also part of this article, since this employment program is still very recent, there is still not enough data for it to be included in table III. In terms of execution in 2022, this program welcomed 15 young people for theoretical training in management, and is still in an initial phase (IEM, *Relatório 2022: Emprego e Coesão Social - Breve Balanço*, 2022). Tables IV and V list the distinctions in percentage of jobs created by gender, educational qualifications, age and previous professional experience.

Table III. Evolution of the CPE, PADE, PEED and CRIEE programs between 2009 and 2022, adapted based on IEM annual balance reports from 2011 to 2022

		2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
CPE	Approved projects	18	21	17	17	17	6	1	2	2	4	1	2	0	1
	Approved jobs (Promoters)	19	22	17	20	18	6	1	2	2	4	1	2	0	1
	Jobs created (Promoters) ¹	6	12	18	26	19	4	2	2	2	2	1	2	0	0
	Financial execution ²	28.577,41€	27.050,92€	29.334,58€	16.515,17€	30.549,67€	5.936,40€	10.977,57€	2.954,10€	13.060,96€	7.104,00€	3.758,44€	0,00€	0,00€	0,00€
PADE, PEED and CRIEE	Approved projects	15	37	28	13	20	45	79	84	67	64	51	35	50	49
	Approved jobs	32	75	44	21	48	81	123	163	123	114	91	56	89	85
	Jobs created ¹	22	46	53	19	23	82	110	157	114	91	110	55	76	77
	Of which Promoters ^{1,3}	16	39	30	14	17	55	77	106	64	57	51	36	47	55
	Financial execution	210.359,86 €	703.229,86 €	1.057.049,47 €	489.415,04 €	464.508,77 €	754.009,52 €	1.051.962,87 €	1.947.129,77 €	1.142.888,17 €	962.425,05 €	1.203.610,26 €	566.047,99 €	774.219,04 €	890.318,98 €

¹ Work stations paid in the following year

² It corresponds to the special subsidy granted by the IEM in cases where the amount of unemployment benefits was not sufficient

³ Work stations created that were Promoters

Table IV. Evolution in percentage of jobs created (Promoters) by gender, educational qualifications, age and previous professional experience of the CPE program, between 2009 and 2022, adapted based on the IEM annual balance reports from 2011 to 2022, calculated by the authors (with the exception of gender and education data for 2011, which were already indicated in the report as a percentage)

		2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	
CPE	Male individual	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	83,3%	61,54%	73,68%	100%	100%	(report does not mention)							
	Level of education	Higher	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	3,85%	10,53%	50%	0%	50%	0%	100%	100%	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)
		Secondary	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	27,8%	38,46%	52,63%	0%	100%	(report does not mention)	0%	0%	0%	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)
		3rd cycle	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	44,4%	23,08%	36,84%	25%	0%	(report does not mention)	50%	0%	0%	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)
		2nd cycle	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	34,62%		25%	0%	(report does not mention)	50%	0%	0%	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)
		1st cycle	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)			0%	0%	(report does not mention)	0%	0%	0%	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)
		No schooling	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	0%		0%	(report does not mention)	0%	0%	0%	0%	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)
	Age	55 years or older	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	11,11%	11,54%	26,32%	"All supported unemployed were adults, essentially aged between 25 and 44 years old."	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)
		Between 45 and 54 years old	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	38,89%	76,92%			0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)
		Between 35 and 44 years old	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)		47,37%		100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)
		Between 25 and 34 years old	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)		(report does not mention)		(report does not mention)	0%	0%	0%	0%	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)
		Between 18 and 24 years old	(report does not mention)		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)				
	Have previous professional experience	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	100%	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)			

Table V. Evolution in percentage of jobs created by gender, educational qualifications, age and previous professional experience of the PADE, PEED and CRIEE programs, between 2009 and 2022, adapted based on the IEM annual balance reports from 2011 to 2022, calculated by the authors

		2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	
PADE, PEED e CRIEE	Male individual	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	43,4%	52,63%	43,48%	39,02%	50,91%	52,23%	47,37%	42,86%	57,27%	60%	46,05%	48,05%	
	Level of education	Higher	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	5,26%	4,35%	18,29%	13,64%	25,48%	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	21,82%	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	19,48%
		Secondary	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	39,62%	42,11%	34,78%	41,46%	34,55%	33,76%	45,61%	37,36%	45,45%	40%	48,68%	54,55%
		3rd cycle	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	26,32%	26,09%	19,51%	25,45%	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	21,98%	(report does not mention)	25,45%	21,05%	(report does not mention)
		2nd cycle	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	24,53%	26,32%	(report does not mention)	16,67%	(report does not mention)							
		1st cycle	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	0%	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	1,82%	8,28%	7,89%	6,59%	4,55%	7,27%	5,26%	(report does not mention)
		No schooling	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	0%	4,35%	1,22%	(report does not mention)							
	Age	55 years or older	(report does not mention)	8,54%	19,09%	21,66%	25,44%	25,27%	(report does not mention)							
		Between 45 and 54 years old	(report does not mention)						(report does not mention)							
		Between 35 and 44 years old	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	77,4%	78,95%	69,57%	79,27%	71,82%	71,34%	64,91%	67,03%	64,55%	74,55%	65,79%	76,62%
		Between 25 and 34 years old	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)												
		Between 18 and 24 years old	(report does not mention)	8,7%	(report does not mention)											
	Have previous professional experience	(report does not mention)	(report does not mention)	96,23%	89,47%	100%	96,34%	100%	89,81%	90,35%	100%	96,36%	94,55%	84,21%	97,4%	

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Starting by analyzing table III in conjunction with table II, it is worth highlighting, right from the start, the drop in the CPE program from 2013 to 2014 (until 2022), which coincided with the change from the PADE program to the PEED program (subsequently replaced by CRIEE). At the same time, it is also verified that this alteration, made the results of the “more generic program” increase, reaching in 2014, 2015 and 2016 successively, the highest values registered in the last years until 2009, in terms of approved projects, jobs approved, jobs created and promoters. Firstly, it is important to point out, before interpreting the referred data, that throughout the annual report of the Madeira Employment Institute (*relatórios Emprego e Coesão Social - Breve Balanço*), of 2011, 2012 and 2013, the justification given for the fact that the CPE continues playing a relevant role at that time, was due to the fact that it continued to be “well received as a solution for creating one's own employment, in a context of retraction and containment in terms of hiring workers” (despite the PADE allowing access to an amount top supports). In this way, the creation of the PEED, by attracting more unemployed entrepreneurs to this program than to the program CPE, fulfilled the IEM's objective of rationalizing resources in a better way, to give greater focus to the creation of jobs in itself, the core objective of this institution. It is suggested that this global change in these entrepreneurship programs was due to the fact that PEED (later replaced by CRIEE) allowed access to higher amounts of funding. There are still applications for the CPE, given the existence of unemployed people who may not be eligible for another program.

From 2017, there was a slight decrease in the PEED program, with some stabilization, and with the introduction of CRIEE coinciding with the emergence of the Covid-19 pandemic, there was a sharp decrease again. 2021 and 2022 suggest a recovery of this event. In the wake of these last few years, it should also be noted that the CPE recorded a financial execution of €0.00 (2020, 2021 and 2022), with no need for a special subsidy for these promoters, that is, from their projects, the use of amounts from unemployment benefits proved to be sufficient. In this way, the channeling of funds from the IEM was centered on the CRIEE program, which was increasingly adapted and worked towards the objective of creating more jobs.

Let us now analyze table IV, which shows the evolution in percentage of jobs created (where all of them are Promoters) by gender, educational qualifications, age and previous professional experience, of the CPE program. Here, we can observe, at least in the period between 2011 and 2015, that there is a tendency for promoters to be more male than female. It should be noted that even though the years 2014 and 2015 had few jobs created (Promoters), where 4 and 2 work stations were created respectively, according to table III, the previous years had, in 2011, 18 jobs created, in 2012 26, and in 2013 19. Hence, when returning to table IV, there are relevant percentages that suggest the trend that in terms of unemployed Madeirans enrolled in the IEM, there was a greater propensity in these years for promoters to be male (although in 2012 the male gender rate registered 61.54%, the year that corresponds to the highest number of jobs created in this program between 2009 and 2022), confirming what was mentioned in Verheul et al. (2005) and Marlow & McAdam (2013).

In terms of educational qualifications, in the CPE program, and given the reduced sample of jobs created (Promoters) between 2015 and 2019, as shown in table III (between 1 and 2 work stations), we chose to focus the analysis between 2011 and 2014. When checking the data in table IV, in conjunction with table III, there is a greater tendency for promoters to have secondary education or the 3rd cycle of basic education. These data suggest that, since the population at the time had a higher rate of population with these levels of education, the same was reflected in the data recorded by the IEM.

In terms of age, there is a greater propensity of promoters from the age of 35 (decreasing with age, confirming what was mentioned in Reynolds et al. (2005) and Shane (2009)), since one of the requirements to be a promoter in the CPE program, is to have unemployment benefits, that is, it presupposes previous professional experiences where Social Security discounts were made. In this sense, and as shown in table IV, the analysis of previous professional experiences within the scope of this program is not relevant.

Entering now the analysis of table V, where the same parameters of the previous table are reflected, but referring to the PADE, PEED and CRIEE programs (which include not only promoters, but also other jobs created for the projects, under the management of the promoters), there is a gender balance over the years 2011 to 2022. In any case, it is important to note that, in the case of jobs created, promoters or non-promoters, it is not possible to determine the propensity for entrepreneurship by gender based on this table. Although this constitutes a limitation to the analysis in terms of entrepreneurial population, we can see that in terms of social inclusion and citizenship, the IEM allies itself with the objective of the regional secretariat where it is framed, by promoting gender equality in the creation of jobs.

With regard to levels of education, there is great emphasis on jobs created at secondary level, and in recent years there has been a tendency for jobs with higher education to grow. The 3rd cycle of basic education also stands out. Alongside the justification given for the CPE program, for these programs, it is suggested that this evolution of jobs follows the evolution of companies and the labor market, which are increasingly competitive and looking for greater specialization of their workers.

With regard to age, it appears that most of the jobs created are centered on the ages between 25 and 44 years old. This is verified since this population corresponds to the one that is most sought after by companies, as a result of the alliance between youth and experience.

In terms of previous professional experiences, it appears that most of the jobs created already had professional experience, suggesting the alliance between the experience previously acquired by the promoters, as a propensity for the risk of entrepreneurship (confirming what was mentioned in Shane (2003) and Van Praag & Versloot (2007)), with the experience previously acquired by the other workers, as a propensity to be selected by the promoters, when choosing the human resources with greater capacity to achieve the success of a company.

It should also be noted, when IEM incentive strategies evolved, the introduction of training courses in the management area, corroborating the arguments of Brush et al. (2003) and Katz and Green (2009), consultancy, strategic increases, simplification of processes and the creation of the eJovem program, factors that should prove to be decisive in the coming years based on the approach to key recipients, closer monitoring of the companies created and raising awareness in management training in order to have greater control over the company's activities with a view to the success of the projects. Special attention is given to the eJovem program as a result of the youth of the recipients, who could become key promoters in issues such as innovation and the introduction of new realities in the Madeiran economy and in its business environment, thus representing an additional measure, closer to young people entrepreneurs. It is suggested that the introduction of this measure emerged in a context in which, in an increasingly global world, realities such as the North American one, in which many young people leave universities and create companies quickly and successfully, can be introduced in a region such as Autonomous Region of Madeira, increasingly internationalized in all contexts.

CONCLUSIONS

After analyzing the data from the Madeira Employment Institute, over the years 2009 to 2022, it appears that one of its main objectives is being met, which is to better rationalize resources, giving greater focus to creation of jobs globally. This was seen as a result of the evolution of the programs over the period under review, where a greater focus on the “more generic program” was found to the detriment of the CPE program, since it is more attractive in financial and technical terms, leading to recipients compete for the program that facilitates the hiring of workers.

The constant concern to get closer to its recipients, unemployed users with entrepreneurial initiative, proves to be an excellent way of achieving the primary objectives of reducing unemployment, and contributing to the improvement of the Madeiran economy. The recent introduction of training courses in the area of management for promoters, consultancy options, strategic increases in terms of hiring the very long-term unemployed, job creation in the areas of the blue, green and/or circular economy, and for projects based in rural councils with a resident population of less than 15 thousand inhabitants, as well as the simplification of processes and the creation of the eJovem programme, are proof of this. Innovation in terms of government policies are key elements for the continuous evolution of programs that are closer to society. A suggestion for future research will be to study the impact of these recent policies in the coming years.

In terms of the characteristics of the jobs created, and in conjunction with the literature review, it was found that, based on the CPE program, there is a greater propensity to entrepreneurship for male individuals, and among young adults, and with the “more generic program”, it was possible to verify that the jobs created tended to be occupied by entrepreneurs or workers who already had previous professional experience, suggesting the confirmation of the literature review in terms of entrepreneurs.

Limitations to the analysis were the data not reflected in the annual balance reports (*relatórios Emprego e Coesão Social - Breve Balanço*), as shown in tables IV and V, as well as the fact that in the PADE, PEED and CRIEE programs, no promoters are distinguished from the other work stations created, in terms of evolution in terms of gender, educational qualifications, age and previous professional experience, which would allow us to better determine the propensity for entrepreneurship according to the characteristics of the promoters. In any case, the CPE program, dealing only with posts that were promoters, brought us closer to this qualification. Thus, another suggestion for future research could be the verification together with the *Instituto de Emprego da*

Madeira, IP-RAM, of the data that were missing in this study, with subsequent analysis. This limitation is not a criticism of the reports prepared, given that the main objective of this institution is the creation of jobs globally, and the specification by promoters only integrates the interest of the theme of entrepreneurship in this study.

IMPLICATIONS

THEORETICAL

For researchers, the present study contributes to the initiation of critical thinking, not only in terms of government institutions that foster entrepreneurship and innovation, but also in regional terms, in which the present study can be used as a comparative in both aspects, to analyze different public services and different regions.

PRACTICAL

For the unemployed, entrepreneurs or non-entrepreneurs, the civil community, the Regional Government of Madeira, and the Madeira Employment Institute, the present study not only contributes to ascertaining the evolution of the programs themselves, and whether the differentiating programs over time had resulted, but also to perceive which aspects can still be improved and worked on. As an example, the fact that the CPE program suggests a greater propensity for entrepreneurship for male individuals, could be an idea to create some kind of incentive for female individuals at this level, similar to the eJovem program, created exclusively for young people.

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